

A Novel Design Solution for Improving Far-field Strain Allowables of Composite Stringer Terminations

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SUMMARY

A novel design principle is presented and tested, which is able to significantly improve the crack initiation loads of aeronautical composite panels with stringer terminations. Taking advantage of the stable crack growth in such structures, an artificial crack is introduced which enhances the combination of bolts and bond line, drastically reducing the strain energy release rate at the run-out tip and increasing the load transfer capability.

Keywords: Stringer Terminations, Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR), Load Transfer, Interlaminar Shear Stresses, Load Eccentricity.

INTRODUCTION

The use of co-cured or co-bonded structures in aerospace offers significant weight reduction over conventional fastened configurations. Unfortunately, the vulnerability of such structures to through-thickness stresses has been highlighted in recent studies [1]. The weakness is particularly exacerbated in thick sectioned run-out regions, where the necessity to terminate stiffeners contrasts with the allowable strain requirements. Run-out tips are in fact critical areas due to geometrical effects and mechanical load paths. The typical currently accepted discrete termination is described in Fig.1. As can be seen, the web is tapered near the termination in order to facilitate the load transfer from the skin to the skin-stiffener section, providing a gradual increase in transverse bending and axial stiffness and relieving local stress concentrations. Furthermore, the foot can be extended beyond the web tip datum plane in order to render the stiffener tip more compliant and capable to follow the skin when it is bent by the secondary bending induced by the eccentricity of the in plane load. The foot tip can also be tapered down to guarantee smoother load transfers and increase the strength to disbond. Ply drop-offs can in fact significantly increase the initial disbond load by 25-30% [2]. In addition, the portion of the skin lying below the termination tip can be thickened locally [3].

However, although promising in terms of global strength, this solution appears penalizing in terms of weight saving. Unfortunately, the overall sensitivity of failure initiation to each parameter appears to be low [1].

Figure 1. Typical design solution of stringer termination

A novel design philosophy is therefore required, which is able to considerably improve the structural strength without penalizing the overall weight. The key driver was identified as the mandatory presence of the bolts at the stiffener tip [4]. Due to certification requirements, the bolts must guarantee a redundant load path in the event of a significantly large skin-stringer disbond. In pristine classical configurations (Fig.2.A), the bolts do not aid load transfer, which occurs due to transverse shear stresses arising within the bond line. Alternatively, if an artificial crack is introduced (non-bonded area 4 in Fig.2.B), a certain amount of load is transferred to the stiffener via the bolt. As a consequence, a smaller amount of load is transferred via the bond line, thus relieving the maximum shear stress at the bond line tip. Let us assume that (the assumption is not restricting) the local strain energy release rate is proportional to the maximum shear stress. It is evident that the alternative design is able to improve the strength proportionally to the decrease of the maximum local shear stress. In the alternative design, the bolts transfer a certain proportion of the total load, thus reducing the amount of load that must be transferred through the bond-line.

Figure 2. Local load transfer in classical (A) and reduced bond line (B) designs.

Furthermore, the peeling mode, which could be prominent in classical design, is highly reduced or even negligible in the alternative design.

Two simple baseline co-cured classical concepts were manufactured and tested. Results were compared to alternative design in order to quantify the obtainable improvement. The test configuration is reported in Fig.3. Stacking sequences are reported in Table 1. The test matrix is reported in Table 2 and in Fig.4.

Fig. 3. Test configuration. Dimensions in mm.

Table 1. Specimen configurations. Stacking sequences.

Baseline	Material	Stacking Sequence	
		Skin	Patch
1	M21/T700	[45/90/-45/0] S	[45/90/-45/0] S
2	M21/T700	[-45/90/45/0] S	[45/90/-45/0] S

Table 2. Specimen configurations. Geometry.

Baseline type (Table 1)	Coupons ID	L	L _P	L _{TEF}	B	L _{tab}	Tot No. of specimens	
1	Baseline	BL-1-1÷3	475	300	--*	56	50	3
	Reduced bond-line	47-1-1÷3	475	300	47	56	50	3
	Reduced bond-line	77-1-1÷3	475	300	77	56	50	3
	Reduced bond-line	107-1-1÷3	475	300	107	56	50	2
2	Baseline	BL-2-1÷3	475	300	--*	56	50	3
	Reduced bond-line	75-2-1÷3	475	300	75	56	50	3

*Fully bonded

Fig. 4. Test coupons' geometry and strain gauges location

DESCRIPTION OF COUPONS

Each coupon is made of two different sub-components:

- a longer component representing the skin
- a shorter patch representing the stiffener

A Teflon layer was inserted between the components in batches 47-1, 77-1, 107-1, and 77-2 (refer to Table 2 for coupon ID) to locally prevent the bonding during the cure.

The skin and patch were co-cured. In order to assess the effect of the mutual orientation of the interface plies, the two baselines have the same lay-ups but different stacking sequences

- +45/+45 skin/patch interface for baseline 1
- -45/+45 skin/patch interface for baseline 2

Furthermore, for configuration 1, three different Teflon lengths were used in order to assess the sensitivity to this parameter. Referring to Fig.4, all the coupons are bolted by means of three rows of two fasteners, with the exception of the 47-1 batch. All the fasteners were EN 6114 6.35 mm diameter, titanium fasteners with countersunk heads. With the exception of the 77-2 batch, all the fasteners were finger tight. Three different values of torque were applied to the coupons of configuration 77-2 in order to assess the sensitivity of failure modes to the bolt torque. All the coupons were C-scanned (Fig. 5) before testing to check the presence of inclusions or damages. No inclusions or damages were found.

Fig. 5. Example of C-scanning

Two back-to-back strain gauges were installed on all the coupons at the crack tip to monitor crack initiation load. Furthermore, white paint and video gauge instrumentation were used to further monitor crack initiation and subsequent propagation.

A ZWICK 1478 testing machine (100kN) was used to test the coupons (Fig.6). All the coupons were tested in tension to final failure.

Fig. 6. Test rig

TEST RESULTS

Test results are reported in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. test results for configuration 1

CONFIGURATION 1 (+45/+45 interface)					
Teflon length, mm	Specimen ID	Crack initiation load, kN	Final failure load, kN	Initial crack location	Failure Mode
Baseline	BL-1-1	27.5	50.2	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
	BL-1-2	27.8	51.4	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
	BL-1-3	30.2	53.1	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
47	47-1-1	No crack initiation	43.5	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	47-1-2	No crack initiation	43.2	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	47-1-3	No crack initiation	43.7	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
77	77-1-1	No crack initiation	52	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	77-1-2	No crack initiation	54.6	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	77-1-3	No crack initiation	50.2	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
107	107-1-1	No crack initiation	50.5	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	107-1-2	No crack initiation	54.5	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C

B= Bolt Bearing NS= Net Section C=Crushing

Table 4. test results for configuration

CONFIGURATION 2 (-45/+45 interface)					
Teflon length, mm	Specimen ID	Crack initiation load, kN	Final failure load, kN	Initial crack location	Failure Mode
Baseline	BL-1-1	26.9	50.3	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
	BL-1-2	28.1	54.5	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
	BL-1-3	29.1	50.6	Bond-line tip	Mixed B/NS/C
77	77-1-1*	No crack initiation	44	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	77-1-2	No crack initiation	46.5	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C
	77-1-3**	No crack initiation	52	N/A	Mixed B/NS/C

* Pre-tensioned bolts ** Loose bolts

Batch BL-1

Crack initiation was evident in all coupons of this batch for values of external load between 27.5 kN and 30.2 kN. The initial crack was located at the bond-line tip. The standard deviation is sufficiently low so that results can be considered to be statistically meaningful. As the load increased, the crack located within the bond-line propagated but other cracks located within the skin were observed in all the coupons, that were located and propagated in a plane parallel to the plane of the bond-line crack. The propagation of the second damage appeared faster than the propagation of the initial crack. All the specimens failed catastrophically at load levels between 50.2 kN and 53.1 kN, showing significant load transfer capability for loads exceeding the crack initiation loads. From visual inspection of the failed coupons (Fig.7), it may be concluded that the final failure is dominated by net-section failure mode localized at the first row of bolts. However, local crushing due to the very large rotation of the cross section (Fig.8) and bolt bearing significantly affect the failure load.

Batch 47-1

The coupons of this batch are bolted with a reduced number of bolts. All the coupons failed catastrophically at loads between 43.2 kN and 43.7 kN. The failure mode and failure location observed are the same as observed for the batch BL-1. No evidence of crack initiation was observed at the bond-line tip.

Batches 77-1 and 107-1

All the coupons failed catastrophically at loads between 50.2 kN and 54.6 kN. No evidence of crack initiation was observed at the bond-line tip. The failure mode and failure location observed are the same as observed for the batches BL-1 and 47-1. The final failure loads, which are increased compared to batch 47-1, show that there is significant sensitivity to the number of bolts and to the total length of the artificial crack. Furthermore, the average failure loads for the two batches are very similar in magnitude, showing that further increments of the length of the unbonded region do not improve the overall performances.

Batch BL-2

Crack initiation was evident in all coupons of this batch for values of external load between 26.9 kN and 29.1 kN. The initial crack was located at the bond-line tip. Once again, the standard deviation is sufficiently low so that results can be considered to be statistically meaningful. As the load increased, the crack located within the bond-line propagated but other cracks located within the skin were observed in all the coupons, which were located and propagated in a plane parallel to the plane of the bond-line crack. The propagation of the second damage appeared faster than the propagation of the initial crack. All the specimens failed catastrophically at load levels between 50.3 kN and 54.5 kN, showing significant load transfer capability for loads exceeding the crack initiation loads. The final failure was dominated by net-section failure mode localized at the first row of bolts. Comparison with baseline 1 shows that there is apparently no macroscopic influence of the interface mutual orientation on the crack initiation and final failure loads.

Batch 75-2

Figure 8 shows the presence of significant local rotation of the cross section at the first row of bolts. This could result in local crushing being induced as the head and/or the nut could be pushed on the laminate, thus introducing significant through-thickness compressive stresses. To assess the influence of local crushing on the final failure load three different values of bolt torque were applied on the three coupons of the batch. Furthermore, from a comparison between this batch and the 77-1, it can be noted that the bond-line tip is not beyond the last row of bolts, but is located at the bolt datum. A first test was performed with pre-tensioned bolts (nominal torque 8.5 Nm). No crack initiation was observed in the bond-line tip area and final failure occurred catastrophically at 44 kN. The failure location and mode were as already observed in all the other tested coupons. A second test was done with finger tight bolts and the final failure was in the same location and apparently due to the same failure mode but at a slightly larger load of 46 kN. The last test was carried out with loose bolts. In this case the bolts acted as pins and neither the head nor the nut were in contact with the

laminates. In this case the final failure load was significantly increased and the coupon failed catastrophically at 52 kN.

Fig. 7. Failed coupon

Fig. 8. Local rotation

CONCLUSIONS

Tests show that crack initiation and subsequent growth are not the critical failure mode for the reduced bond-line configurations, as there was no evidence of delamination and/or disbond in reduced bond-line coupons up to the failure load.

Final failure occurred in reduced bond-line coupons mainly due to net section failure mode. Hence, it was impossible to quantify the level of improvement provided by the novel design in terms of crack initiation at the bond-line tip.

However, it can be concluded that no cracks initiated for loads that doubled the crack initiation loads for classical designs.

It was impossible to observe and measure changes in global stiffness of the coupons from the load vs. crosshead displacement curves (Fig.9), since crack initiation and growth are localized phenomena.

From the reading of load vs. displacement curve it might be erroneously concluded that no detrimental effects are caused by crack growth.

Apart from the main crack plane (at the skin/stiffener interface), multiple parallel damages were observed, which propagated as quick as the main disbond.

The +45/-45 interface does not seem to improve the crack initiation load. It may affect propagation due to fibre bridging, but not initiation.

From direct comparison between batch 47-1 and all other reduced bond-line tests, it is concluded that adding a third row of fasteners alleviates the bolt loads and delays the catastrophic failure.

Fig. 9. Example of Load vs. Cross-head displacement curve

Fig. 10. Strain gauge measurements

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